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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****PATIENT'S SATISFACTION AFTER PILONIDAL SINUS
EXCISION UNDER LOCAL ANAESTHESIA****Dr. Sara Tahir¹, Dr. Hira Yaqub², Dr. Shabana³**¹Email: saratahir1234@gmail.com²Email: hirayaqub2424@gmail.com³Email: shabanamalik.malik@gmail.com^{1,2,3}King Edward Medical University/Mayo Hospital, Lahore**Article Received:** December 2020**Accepted:** December 2020**Published:** January 2021**Abstract:**

Introduction: Pilonidal disease is a morbid condition of the young population that could impair quality of life with a high cost for the health care system. No consensus exists on optimal surgical treatment, even if several techniques have been proposed. (Giuseppe et al., 2019) The incidence of pilonidal sinus disease is increasing globally. (Doll et al., 2019) About 100/100,000 inhabitants per year are affected in Germany, with even higher numbers reported for Turkey. (Doll et al., 2015b, Duman et al., 2017)

Methodology: Study Design: Descriptive case series.

Setting: Department of Surgery, DHQ Hospital, Sahiwal.

Duration: The duration of the study was from September 2019 to June 2020.

Sample Size: Sample size of 31 cases

Sampling Technique: Non probability, consecutive sampling.

Data Collection Procedure: 31 patients fulfilling the selection criteria was included in this study from wards of Department of Surgery, DHQ Hospital, Sahiwal. An informed consent was obtained. Demographic profile (name, age, gender, and duration of pilonidal sinus, h/o any surgery, type of anesthesia taken that time) was also obtained. Then patients underwent surgery by a single surgical team under local anesthesia with assistance of researcher. Surgical excision was done as per standard protocol.

Results: The pain frequency and severity recorded following the operation and presented in Table 1. As shown in this table, frequency of pain in local anesthesia surgery patients was significantly lower in 3h, 6h, 24h, and 48h after surgery ($P < 0.001$). Furthermore, the average of pain score was significantly higher in local anesthesia surgery patients at 3h and 6h after surgery ($P < 0.001$). All patients who underwent local anesthesia surgery patients received Xylocaine injection.

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INTRODUCTION:

Pilonidal disease is a morbid condition of the young population that could impair quality of life with a high cost for the health care system. No consensus exists on optimal surgical treatment, even if several techniques have been proposed. (Giuseppe et al., 2019) The incidence of pilonidal sinus disease is increasing globally. (Doll et al., 2019) About 100/100,000 inhabitants per year are affected in Germany, with even higher numbers reported for Turkey. (Doll et al., 2015b, Duman et al., 2017).

Since 2013, American, German and Italian societies have published guidelines on best clinical practice. (Segre et al., 2015, Steele et al., 2013, Iesalnieks et al., 2016) With pilonidal sinus disease incidence increasing and patients freely choosing their surgeon, patients' interest issues have been brought forward estimating patient satisfaction following pilonidal sinus surgery. The influence of wound healing time and long-term recurrence rate on patient satisfaction in primary pilonidal sinus disease surgery has not been investigated yet. (Doll et al., 2015a)

METHODOLOGY:

Study Design: Descriptive case series.

Setting: Department of Surgery, DHQ Hospital, Sahiwal.

Duration: The duration of the study was from September 2019 to June 2020.

Sample Size: Sample size of 31 cases

RESULTS:

Table 1 shows the frequency and severity of pain after surgery in local anaesthesia

Estimation Time		Local Anaesthesia	P value
3 hours after surgery	mean±SD	1.88±1.21	0.002
	Frequency	17(56.7%)	<0.0001
6 hours after surgery	mean±SD	1.70±0.91	0.002
	Frequency	17(56.7%)	<0.0001
24 hours after surgery	mean±SD	2.14±0.90	0.55
	Frequency	7(23.3%)	<0.0001
48 hours after surgery	mean±SD	-	-
	Frequency	1(3.3%)	<0.003
72 hours after surgery	mean±SD	-	-
	Frequency	0	<0.07

The pain frequency and severity recorded following the operation and presented in Table 1. As shown in this table, frequency of pain in local anesthesia surgery patients was significantly lower in 3h, 6h, 24h, and 48h after surgery ($P<0.001$). Furthermore, the average of pain score was significantly higher in local anesthesia surgery patients at 3h and 6h after surgery ($P<0.001$). All patients who underwent local anesthesia surgery patients received Xylocaine injection.

The hospital stay was 1.03 ± 0.50 days for the local anesthesia surgery patients. Statistically significant difference was observed in the hospital stay in local anesthesia surgery patients ($P=0.19$).

Sampling Technique: Non probability, consecutive sampling.

Sample Selection**Inclusion Criteria:**

- Patients of age 16-65years of either gender presenting with pilonidal sinus (as per operational definition).

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with ASA III or IV
- Patients with recurrent disease
- Patients undergoing redo surgery for previous failed surgery
- Diabetes (BSR>200mg/dl)
- Surgery required >30minutes

Data Collection Procedure: 31 patients fulfilling the selection criteria was included in this study from wards of Department of Surgery, DHQ Hospital, Sahiwal. An informed consent was obtained. Demographic profile (name, age, gender, and duration of pilonidal sinus, h/o any surgery, type of anesthesia taken that time) was also obtained. Then patients underwent surgery by a single surgical team under local anesthesia with assistance of researcher. Surgical excision was done as per standard protocol. Then after surgery, patients were shifted in post-surgical wards and was followed-up there for 72 hours. During 72 hours, patients were evaluated for satisfaction from anesthesia applied. If patient was satisfied with anesthesia technique, no complaint of pain, nausea or vomiting, then patient satisfaction was labeled.

The average of the time in return to work was 10.93 ± 5.75 days for the local anesthesia surgery patients ($P=0.61$).

DISCUSSION:

Due to the fact that the pilonidal disease is usually seen in young adults and the estimated incidence is 26 per 100000 people, the selection of an appropriate method of surgery and anesthesia for reducing pain, recurrence, the operation duration and the length of the hospital stay is significant (Mentes et al., 2006; Søndena et al., 1995; Yalcin & Ergul, 2010). Thereby, in this study, all the 31 participants underwent a primary closure. The patients who undergo the primary closure, the duration of returning to the normal activity and the wound healing is shorter but the wound infection and recurrence is less compared with the open healing (McCallum, King, & Bruce, 2008). Several studies refer to the local and spinal anesthesia as alternative methods to the general anesthesia for the pilonidal sinus surgery (Schmittner et al., 2013). In this study, an analysis is made in local anesthesia surgery patients in the pain intensity, recovery time, the length of the hospital stay, and the complications. Pain is one of the most effective factors which could affect the quality of patients' life after a surgery. Many attempts have been done to select an appropriate surgery and anesthesia method to reduce the patients' pain during and after the surgery (Yalcin & Ergul, 2010; Møiniche et al., 2002). In this study, the patients in the local anesthesia surgery patients experienced less pain during 48 hours following the surgery which was in concordance with the study of Naja et al. (Naja, Ziade, & El-Rajab, 2003) and Sungurtekin et al. (Sungurtekin et al., 2003). In this study, the most significant difference in the pain intensity was experienced during 4 hours following the surgery. Also, Tverskoy et al. conducted a study on the surgery of inguinal hernia using different anesthesia methods and reported that during 48 hours following the surgery the patients in the local anaesthesia group experienced less pain compared with the general anaesthesia group.

CONCLUSION:

This study revealed that administration of the local anesthesia for the pilonidal sinus surgery was associated with the decreased pain during 48 hours following the surgery, shorter recovery time, and the less consumption of painkillers. Therefore, the local anesthesia can be used as an appropriate substitute for the general anesthesia in the pilonidal sinus surgery.

REFERENCES:

1. Doll, D.; Luedi, M. M.; Evers, T.; Kauf, P. & Matevossian, E. 2015a. Recurrence-free survival,

but not surgical therapy per se, determines 583 patients' long-term satisfaction following primary pilonidal sinus surgery. *Int J Colorectal Dis*, 30, 605-11.

2. Doll, D.; Luedi, M. M. M. M.; Wieferich, K.; van der Zypen, D.; Maak, M. & Glanemann, M. 2015b. Stop insulting the patient: neither incidence nor recurrence of pilonidal sinus disease is linked to personal hygiene. *Pilonidal Sinus Journal*, 1, 11-18.
3. Doll, D.; Orlik, A.; Maier, K.; Kauf, P.; Schmid, M.; Diekmann, M.; Vogt, A. P.; Stauffer, V. K. & Luedi, M. M. 2019. Impact of geography and surgical approach on recurrence in global pilonidal sinus disease. *Scientific Reports*, 9, 15111.
4. Duman, K.; Girgin, M. & Harlak, A. 2017. Prevalence of sacrococcygeal pilonidal disease in Turkey. *Asian journal of surgery*, 40, 434-437.
5. Elgohary, H. & Oraby, E. 2015. Pilonidal sinus: minimal excision and primary closure under local anesthesia. *The Egyptian Journal of Surgery*, 34, 287-292.
6. Ghazawi, S. B. A.-. 2004. The Effect of Anesthetic Techniques in Pilonidal Sinus Surgery. *Bahrain Medical Bulletin*, 26, 1-4.
7. Giuseppe, F.; Silvia, D. G.; Patrizia, R.; Riccardo, P.; Antonio, D. S.; Aldo, R. S.; Angela, I.; Pietro, M.; Domenico, M. & Luciano, T. 2019. Pilonidal sinus disease: Preliminary case-control study on heat-related wound dehiscence. *Ann Med Surg (Lond)*, 48, 144-149.
8. Iesalnieks, I.; Ommer, A.; Petersen, S.; Doll, D. & Herold, A. 2016. German national guideline on the management of pilonidal disease. *Langenbeck's archives of surgery*, 401, 599-609.
9. Sadeghian, I. 2016. Pilonidal sinus operations performed under local anesthesia versus the general anesthesia: clinical trial study. *Global journal of health science*, 8,
10. McCallum, I. J., King, P. M., & Bruce, J. (2008). Healing by primary closure versus open healing after surgery for pilonidal sinus: systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ*. 336(7649), 868-71.
11. McCallum, I., King, P. M., & Bruce, J. (2007). Healing by primary versus secondary intention after surgical treatment for pilonidal sinus. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*, 4(4).
12. Bagci, M., Bilgin, T., Coskun, I., Ozgul, O., & Ozdemir, M. (2006). Management of pilonidal sinus disease with oblique excision and primary

- closure: results of 493 patients. *Diseases of the colon & rectum*, 49(1), 104-8.
13. Møiniche, S., Kehlet, H., & Dahl, J. B. (2002). A qualitative and quantitative systematic review of preemptive analgesia for postoperative pain relief: the role of timing of analgesia. *Anesthesiology*, 96(3), 725-41.
 14. Muzi, M. G., Milito, G., Cadeddu, F., Nigro, C., Andreoli, F., Amabile, D., et al. (2010). Randomized comparison of Limberg flap versus modified primary closure for the treatment of pilonidal disease. *The American Journal of Surgery*, 200(1), 9-14.
 15. Naja, M., Ziade, M., & El-Rajab, M. (2003). Sacrococcygeal local anaesthesia versus general anaesthesia for pilonidal sinus surgery: A prospective randomised trial. *Anaesthesia*, 58(10), 1007-12.
 16. Pelosi, P., Croci, M., Calappi, E., Cerisara, M., Mulazzi, D., Vicardi, P., et al. (1995). The prone positioning during general anesthesia minimally affects respiratory mechanics while improving functional residual capacity and increasing oxygen tension. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*, 80(5), 955-60.
 17. Schmittner, M. D., Dieterich, S., Gebhardt, V., Weiss, C., Burmeister, M. A., Bussen, D. G., et al. (2013). Randomised clinical trial of pilonidal sinus operations performed in the prone position under spinal anaesthesia with hyperbaric bupivacaine 0.5% versus total intravenous anaesthesia. *International journal of colorectal disease*, 28(6), 873-80.